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Abstract

This work developed the models of vehicle concept and hybrid system in a vehicle, the proposal includes characterization on light and recent materials developed, add an efficient electric motor, fuel cell system, and batteries recently available on the market with new technology, which will increase the autonomy of the vehicles, is a project that tries to show an electric vehicle, new design, adequate to the city. In automotive manufacture and design are very wide activities to develop a new product in the world, so in this case was focused on appearance, power system, and CAE analysis. The material that was selected aluminum alloy is used in commercial cars; the alloy does not have a commercial name for this situation the phases of materials contained in the alloy. This is possible with the technique of X-ray diffraction. The CAE analysis allowed the adequate model of the vehicle to have a stress lower than the materials under analysis.

Keywords: Electric vehicles; Hybrid systems; Fuel cell system; CAE; Simulation.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In recent years the world has developed different proposals using a variety of fuels, there are hybrid cars, electric cars, hydrogen motors, fuel cell systems[1]. In the world increased demand for electric vehicles for example in the Philippines there are different brands such as Cherry, Hyundai, Geely, Mitsubishi, Toyota, and Nissan. The brands have hybrid systems in energy that are available in the market at this time[2]. In China electric vehicles have grown stronger whose fleet increased from 11,600 to 350,000 between 2012 and 2016, and over 2 million vehicles in 2019. China has brands such as BYD, followed by Renault–Nissan, Tesla, and BMW[3], while in U.S.A. the President Biden works for a rapid internal combustion engine vehicles to “zero emission vehicles”, there are different types as plug-in electric vehicles (PEVs), hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs), the last one has significant market penetration in the heavy-duty on diverse brands in sector before 2030, the light-duty sector is dominated by PEVs[4], at the similar period. Some of the offerings the Nissan Leaf, the Toyota Prius Prime, the Chevrolet Bolt, Tesla Model 3s, Model Ys, and the Mitsubishi Outlander PHEV have been commercialized [5].

The different options for the manufacture of electric and hybrid vehicles allowed to development of electric or hybrid vehicles with high or low velocity[6] and displacements limited in function on available energy[7], the cost could be cheap or expensive depending on the technology and materials used, a way is traced to reduce cost on the next years. Every five years there are significant advantages, batteries with high capacity[8], motors with more energy power, and lighter materials, every advantage gives the opportunity to develop new proposals with a better option in vehicles [9], the opportunity is the development of a vehicle to move in the city and is necessary it can will be used between near to cities o 60 kilometers in sporadic occasions[10], it solve displacements to persons in the cities to every day with zero emissions and is necessary a determinate quantity of energy available.

1.1 Fuel cell system

The fuel cell system is a good option for alternative fuels, it system provides energy controlled with higher efficiency than conventional power plants, the system converts hydrogen energy to electric energy, and generates water as a by-product being environmentally friendly with respect to the use of oil and petroleum products. Compared to gasoline the fuel cells have fewer efficiency losses, zero, and no thermal losses derivate of parts in movement. Fuel cell systems are sources of renewable energy (green energy) it does not generate as dangerous emissions as Nitrous Oxides (NOx), and they work with exceptionally low noise levels [11]. In a fuel cell system, the hydrogen in the cell generates a chemical reaction using oxidant elements. If the cell is supplied with fuel and an oxidant, electrical power is obtained. The fuel cell could not use the battery if the energy demanded by the system is generated by the system or well the system too can supply energy to batteries, it depends on the design of the system.

1.2 CAD-CAE Model

This work shows the models of the parts and electrical vehicle proposal using a system of energy based on fuel cells and batteries of high technology, various designs were developed previously different proposals of electric vehicles, but now this proposal has the opportunity to get batteries with major capacity, there are new motors with low weight and considerable power to get a better vehicle in a new concept to have an utility vehicle to the city and capacity to move to distances on 50 kilometers, designed with light materials but with high resistance. The model was evaluated using the software CAD-CAE to get adequate conditions under mechanical design.

2.0 METHODS AND MATERIAL

The idea of a light vehicle was discussed on the possible way to develop a new proposal with the capacity to run at 80 km/h, on the proposal was oriented to a vehicle designed for two persons and get space to travel objects to the city market or others possible situations that need the users, the idea contain a simple vehicle with cover to the sun. The idea was developed

in general over the paper news products, and the manuscripts were reviewed, and evaluated to get a new proposal on the vehicle. This project is not about traditional cars; the idea is a simple vehicle with high technology with zero emissions.

Elements.

1. Car body (Aluminum alloy)
2. Commercial wheels
3. Structure
4. Battery Ion Lithium 48V, 26ah 3300W
5. Electric motor, 2000W, 48V Brushless Motor Kit 4300 rpm
6. Commercial suspension system

7. Car cover (Aluminum alloy)
8. Fuel cell system 3000 W, 72 cell, Horizon H-3000
9. Others

The aerodynamic analysis of the vehicle was evaluated with CAD-CAE software. The aluminum alloy proposal has been evaluated with X-Ray Diffractometer Bruker D8 advance to show the phases that are present in the alloy as material, it is necessary to show the phases derivate of is used in cars but it hasn't commercial name in plate. The hardness was tested with a durometer Mitutoyo Wizzard.

Table 1.

Software conditions

Unit System:	SI
Analysis Type:	External (exclude internal spaces)
Size of Computational Domain	
Axis Size	
X min	-0.371 m
X max	0.724 m
Y min	-0.237 m
Y max	0.493 m
Z min	-0.760 m
Z max	0.204 m
X size	1.095 m
Y size	0.731 m
Z size	0.964 m

Table 2.

Conditions loaded in software

Ambient Conditions	
Thermodynamic parameters	Static Pressure: 101325.00 Pa Temperature: 293.20 K
Velocity parameters	Velocity vector Velocity in X direction: 0 m/s Velocity in Y direction: 0 m/s Velocity in Z direction: 80.000 m/s
Turbulence parameters	Turbulence intensity and length Intensity: 0.10 % Length: 0.005 m

The energy was balanced by getting a Fuel Cell System Horizon that generates 3,000W, while the electric motor demands 2,000W, the battery as support was designed to 3,300W, in the vehicle was considered

one battery in case the system will have some problem with energy, in this case, is necessary as new proposal.

Methodology diagram

Figure 1. Diagram used to the project

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The idea was developed in various steps, and the structure and elements were modified at different times. The modeling was developed using CAD software for seven months, the parts were made starting with the structure, and its idea was modified on different occasions, the first part modeled is shown in Figure 2 being the base of the structure design.

The model was designed step by step, so Figure 2 shows the parts developed for an electric vehicle, in the figure it is possible to identify the space for the driver, the body car model, the proposal on a specific design, the materials, and the shape of the vehicle, the idea on the light vehicle to move in the city with a velocity of 80 km/h.

Figure 2. Body car and structure basic model

3.1 Evaluation of phases in alloy used in car body

The material proposed for the car body is an aluminum alloy used in the automotive industry developed by suppliers of automotive alloys, it material is light and with adequate mechanical resistance to

absorb energy, it alloy has a hardness of 36.5 HR 15N tested in durometer, the alloy has the phases identified with X-Ray Diffractometer in the research laboratory of university (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Phases in aluminum alloy

3.2 Conceptualization

The image of the concept of the vehicle appears in Figure 4, in the figures is possible to appreciate the suspension's basic system of shock absorbers in the four

wheels, in general in the vehicle is a basic system of high technology on various elements, it with the idea to avoid possible failures with complex systems to get a vehicle reduced in risks on systems used.

Figure 4. Electric Vehicle

The Fuel Cell System was positioned in the back space of the vehicle, so there are batteries and a motor as was shown in Figure 5, in that space are fixed the

diverse elements to generate the energy, and it allows a system with 3,000W generated with the demand of energy in electric motor on 2,000W.

Figure 5. Space to energy system

The Fuel Cell System was developed in the model with the basis of a structure of a prototype used in the laboratory (Figure 6), it system in the laboratory contains an electric motor (M), a battery (B) to supply energy to the controller (C), the last one allow the operation of the Fuel Cell (FC) to generate energy to an

electric motor, the Fuel Cell need hydrogen under controller pressure and a water tank (WT) produced in chemical reaction, the supply of hydrogen is possible with pressure regulator (PR), finally is necessary the hydrogen tank (HT) to supply the gas [12].

Figure 6. Elements in fuel cell system in laboratory

3.3 Analisis CAE

The aerodynamic analysis was evaluated using CAD-CAE software, the analysis was on a velocity of 80 km/h as other authors considered for evaluations [13], the results in Figure 7 show pressures on 0.107 Mega Pascals (MPa), its value is lower than the

mechanical resistance of the materials as Aluminum 70 MPa, 7000 series 380 MPa used on the design of vehicle [14], it allowed get out an electric vehicle with good conditions to operate in short displacements and get sufficient autonomy.

Figure 7. Aerodynamic simulation

The cost and the weight of the vehicle are considered in the values shown in Table 3, the total weight is 229 kg, which is similar to the vehicle developed by Fernandes [15], and the results obtained

by Lin [16]. The stages of design were used on tree stages as Fang showed in manuscript based in simulation [17].

Table 3.

Element	Approximate weight of vehicle	
	Price (USD)	Weight (kg)
Fuel Cell	14,800	46
Structure of Aluminum	800	40
Wheels	60	3
Electric Motor	240	10
Battery	110	10
Accessories and parts	3,200	120
Total:	19,210	229

CONCLUSIONS

The electric vehicle proposal was modeled using CAD-CAE software, the new concept was based on a structure of aluminum getting low weight and incorporated elements of a Fuel Cell System, the results allowed add an electric motor commercial and battery with the demand of energy necessary for displacements of the vehicle in the city, the aerodynamic analysis was evaluated on lineal velocity similar to others projects of cars of 80 km/h getting values of mechanical stress lower than the mechanical resistance of the materials selected, the material used on car body evaluated with X-Ray Diffraction allowed identify the different phases in the material as new information.

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